

A resurrected ancestor of Cas12a expands target access and substrate recognition for nucleic-acid editing and detection

Ylenia Jabalera^{1,8}, Igor Tascón^{2,3,8}, Sara Samperio¹, Jorge P. López-Alonso^{3,4}, Monika Gonzalez-Lopez¹, Ana M. Aransay^{1,5}, Guillermo Abascal-Palacios^{2,3}, Chase L. Beisel^{6,7}, Iban Ubarretxena-Belandia^{2,3*} & Raul Perez-Jimenez^{1,2*}

¹CICbioGUNE, Basque Research & Technology Alliance (BRTA), Bizkaia Technology Park, Building 800, 48160 Derio, Bizkaia, Spain.

²Ikerbasque Foundation for Science, Bilbao, Spain.

³Instituto Biofisika (UPV/EHU, CSIC), University of the Basque Country, Leioa, Spain.

⁴Basque Resource for Electron Microscopy, Leioa, Spain.

⁵CIBERehd, ISCIII, 28029 Madrid, Spain.

⁶Helmholtz Institute for RNA-based Infection Research, Helmholtz Centre for Infection Research, Würzburg, Germany.

⁷Medical Faculty, University of Würzburg, Würzburg, Germany

⁸These authors contributed equally to the work.

*Corresponding authors: ivan.ubarrechena@ehu.eus (I. U-B) and raulpje@cicbiogune.es (R.P-J).

Summary

Cas12a nucleases offer powerful tools for genome editing and molecular diagnostics, yet their existing properties constrict the range of accessible targets and applications. Here, we apply ancestral sequence reconstruction (ASR) to a set of Cas12a orthologs from hydrobacteria to reconstruct a common ancestor (ReChb) that yields near-PAMless targeting and the recognition of diverse nucleic-acid activators and collateral substrates. ReChb shares 53% sequence identity with the closest Cas12a ortholog; however, ReChb no longer requires a T-rich PAM and can achieve genome editing in human cells at sites inaccessible to the natural FnCas12a or the engineered and PAM-flexible EnAsCas12a. Furthermore, ReChb can be triggered not only by double-stranded DNA but also by single-stranded RNA and DNA targets, which leads to non-specific collateral cleavage of all three nucleic-acid substrates with similar efficiencies. Finally, tertiary and quaternary structures of ReChb obtained by cryo-EM reveal the molecular details underlying its expanded biophysical activities. Overall, ReChb expands the application space of Cas12a nucleases and underscores the potential of ASR for enhancing CRISPR technologies.

Introduction

Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats (CRISPR) and their CRISPR-associated (Cas) nucleases confer bacteria and archaea with adaptive immunity against foreign mobile genetic elements¹⁻⁴. These CRISPR-Cas systems rely on the ability of the nucleases to use a CRISPR RNA (crRNA) as a guide, with the additional requirement of a non-self sequence (i.e., protospacer-adjacent motif (PAM) in DNA, protospacer-flanking sequence (PFS) in RNA) flanking the complementary nucleic-acid target. Target recognition then enacts a myriad of immune activities, from cutting target nucleic acids to inducing cellular dormancy or cell death through widespread RNA or DNA degradation. The adeptness of Cas nucleases at RNA-guided targeting of nucleic acids has catapulted their repurposing for genome editing and diagnostics among many applications⁵. Founded on Cas9 from *Streptococcus pyogenes* (SpCas9)^{6,7}, the catalogue of Cas nucleases has been expanded with the discovery of variants of the compact CRISPR class 2 system, including orthologs of Cas9, Cas12 and Cas13 nucleases^{2,5,8-11}. In particular, Cas12a nucleases offer a promising alternative to Cas9 due to relying on T-rich PAMs, generating staggered double-strand breaks in their DNA target, and using a short crRNA with no need for a transactivating-crRNA (tracrRNA). Also, Cas12a nucleases can process their own crRNA lending to multiplexing and exert fewer off-targets^{12,13}. Finally, activated Cas12a collaterally cleave single-stranded (ss)DNA, which has been used for signal amplification as part of CRISPR-based molecular diagnostics¹⁴.

Despite the successful implementation of Cas nucleases as technologies, these natural counterparts and ideal technological components remain far apart⁹. To bridge this gap, molecular engineering has been the basis for the development of improved CRISPR tools with expanded capabilities¹⁵⁻¹⁸. In the case of Cas12a, engineered versions relying on a few mutations to natural nucleases such as Cas12a from *Acidaminococcus sp* (AsCas12a), *Lachnospiraceae bacterium* (LbCas2a) and *Francisella novicida* (FnCas12a) have broadened PAM preferences^{17,19-21}. Other mutations have been reported to improve editing efficiencies²², and efforts have been made to expand substrate recognition, such as the recognition of RNA substrates by the PAM distal end of the crRNA²³. Nevertheless, even these engineered forms of Cas12a still exhibit properties that at most partially deviate from their natural counterparts.

To overcome these limitations, we adopted a distinct approach based on Ancestral Sequence Reconstruction (ASR). Using ASR, we previously resurrected active Cas9 nucleases that no longer exist in nature¹⁵. These proteins, derived from type II-A Cas9 orthologs from *Clostridia* and *Bacilli* classes, retraced the evolution of Cas9 up until modern *Streptococcus pyogenes* Cas9 and displayed PAM-flexible target recognition, gRNA and substrate promiscuity, and even collateral cleavage. While the ancient Cas9 orthologs lost the ability to cleave dsDNA and exhibited limited genome editing activity as dual nickases, the orthologs suggested that ancestral reconstruction could unlock expanded properties of functions of other Cas nucleases. Here, we apply ASR to engineer a fully functional, resurrected Cas nuclease derived from orthologs of Cas12a from hydrobacteria phyla^{14,24}. The resulting resurrected Cas12a ancestor, which we call ReChb, yielded PAM-flexible editing in human cells across three cell lines, seven genes and 16 target sites that outperformed natural and engineered Cas12a nucleases EnAsCas12a¹⁷ and could both target and collaterally cleave RNA, ssDNA and dsDNA. ReChb thus offers a unique and versatile tool for a multitude of CRISPR-based biotechnological applications, from gene therapy to molecular diagnostics.

Results

Applying Ancestral Sequence Resurrection of Cas12a nucleases to generate ReChb

To reconstruct the sequence of ReChb using ASR, we first collected sixty-three homologs of Cas12a sequences from species belonging to the phyla *Pseudomonadota*, *Planctomycetota*,

Spirochaetota, *Bacteroidota*, belonging to the clade hydrobacteria, and *Bacillota* (as outgroup) (**Fig. 1a and Extended Data Fig. 1**). A phylogeny using Bayesian inference was constructed following previously described methods¹⁵. The internal node representing a common ancestor of hydrobacteria (excluding the outgroup) was selected for resurrection, resulting in an amino-acid sequence with 53% identity shared with the *Francisella novicida* Cas12a (FnCas12a)²⁴ and a posterior probability average of 0.92. This ancestor is estimated to have diverged around 3,000 Mya, CI: 2978.5-3030.4 Mya (ref.²⁵). The alignment of the reconstructed ReChb against representative sequences from the other phyla shows substantial differences in the REC1 domain (**Fig. 1b**) with a K-rich region unique to ReChb. Also, of note is the presence of a tryptophan (W1041) in a highly conserved region of the RuvC-II domain (**Fig. 1b**), which is conserved in uncharacterized Cas12a sequences from *Planctomycetota* and *Spirochaetota* but is absent in the other orthologs (**Supplementary Fig. 1**). The reconstructed sequence was synthesized and expressed in *Escherichia coli* with higher expression yields than FnCas12a (**Supplementary Fig. 2**).

ReChb efficiently edits human cells

FnCas12a, the query sequence for ReChb, has been shown to display variable genome editing activity in human cells^{12,24,26}, while the ancestral Cas9 nucleases did not exhibit any measurable editing activity when targeting a single site. To evaluate the editing activity of ReChb, we quantified the formation of insertions or deletions (indels) via the generation of dsDNA breaks in HEK293 cells using crRNA guides from FnCas12a targeting sites flanked by a canonical 5'-TTTV-3' PAM in the genes *DNMT1* (5'-TTTC-3'), *AAVSI* (5'-TTTG-3') and *EMXI* (5'-TTTG-3'). After transiently transfecting ReChb and crRNA expression constructs, we employed a T7 endonuclease mismatch assay to quantify indel formation. Compared to FnCas12a, which only exhibited detectable indel formation (1%) at *AAVSI*, ReChb displayed robust indel formation (15-35%) against the target in each of the three genes (**Extended Data Fig. 2a-b**). Considering that only a limited number of type II and V orthologs have been successfully employed for genome editing in mammalian cells, these results highlight the potential of ReChb as a gene-editing tool.

ReChb exhibits robust PAM-flexible editing in human cells

Given the PAM flexibility of the ancestral version of SpCas9 (ref.¹⁵), we next explored the PAM requirements for ReChb. We applied an *in vitro* cleavage assay in which purified ReChb loaded with an *in vitro*-transcribed crRNA complex was incubated with a linear DNA target flanked seven random nucleotides. The PAM-containing cut DNA fragment was then gel purified and submitted for amplicon sequencing (**Fig. 2a**). The resulting normalized read counts revealed a modest preference for C/T at the -2 and -3 positions (**Fig. 2b,c**). However, all sequences were identified in the gel-extracted DNA (**Source of Data 1**), suggesting that the resurrected nuclease has PAM biases but no obvious requirements. This PAM-flexible activity was verified *in vitro* using both the non-T-rich PAM sequences 5'-ATTG-3', 5'-ATTT-3', 5'-ACCC-3', 5'-ATCA-3' and 5'-ATGG-3' on a supercoiled plasmid, as well as 5'-TAAA-3', 5'-TCCC-3', and 5'-TGGG-3' on a FAM-labelled dsDNA substrate (**Supplementary Fig. 3**). Given the parallels to the PAM flexibility of the ancestral form of SpCas9¹⁵, flexible PAM recognition could be a general feature of resurrected Cas nucleases.

After demonstrating the ability of ReChb to target non-canonical sites *in vitro*, we evaluated its targeting flexibility in human cells in comparison to the engineered Cas12a variant enAsCas12a (ref.¹⁷). enAsCas12a nuclease was selected because it has been associated with the broadest PAM recognition of Cas12a nucleases to-date, with recognition of canonical numerous non-canonical PAMs¹⁷. To provide a more comprehensive analysis, we targeted 13 sites in four human genes (*DNMT1*, *CFTR*, *FANC* and *RUNX*) and analysed the frequency of indels by Sanger-based indel detection methodology, which provides precise results for indels with a frequency above 1-2%²⁷. These experiments yielded robust and editing activities (ranges 30-37%) at two target sites with a canonical PAM (5'-TTTC-3', 5'-TTTG-3'). Jabalera, Y., Tascón, I., Samperio, S. et al. A resurrected ancestor of Cas12a expands target access and substrate recognition for nucleic acid editing and detection. *Nat Biotechnol* 43, 1663–1672 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-024-02461-3>

3') as well as two target sites with T/C-rich PAM (5'-TCCT-3', 5'-TCCC-3') PAMs (ranges 22-29%), but also at sites with PAMs not recognized efficiently by enAsCas12a such as 5'-TCGG-3' (40%), 5'-TATT-3' (38%), 5'-AGTT-3' (17%) or 5'-TGTT-3' (17%) (**Fig. 2d**). At four sites with a 5'-TTAC-3', 5'-TCGC-3', 5'-CGGT-3' or 5'-TAAC-3' PAM, both nucleases yielded poor indel frequencies (< 5%), either due to limited PAM recognition or other factors such as poor sgRNA performance or site accessibility. Across the other sites, ReChb efficiently edited those targeted by enAsCas12a and, more importantly, demonstrated robust genome editing at sites not recognized by enAsCas12a (**Fig. 2e**). These data show that ReChb enables robust editing of sites with non-canonical PAMs, with a tested PAM preference towards 5'-NYYN-3', 5'-NRYN-3' and 5'-NYRN-3' in eukaryotic cells, extending beyond those recognized by enAsCas12a. Additionally, ReChb could drive indel formation when transfected as a ribonucleoprotein (RNP) complex in two other cell lines (HeLa and Hs27 fibroblast cells) (**Supplementary Fig. 4**). Across the four target sites in four genes (*DNMT1*, *SOD1*, *FANCF*, *CFTR*) representing both canonical and non-canonical PAMs, ReChb showed robust editing between 10-60%. Finally, off-target analysis of five on-target sites revealed that the indel frequencies at the predicted/potential off-target sites²⁸ were below 1% (**Source of Data 2**), much lower than those at corresponding on-target sites. Thus, ReChb exhibits PAM-flexible editing in human cells that outperforms enAnCas12a in a head-to-head comparison.

ReChb accepts RNA, ssDNA and dsDNA targets and collateral substrates as well as altered crRNAs

Given the broadened PAM recognition of ReChb as one biochemical feature of this nuclease, we explored whether it can expand beyond dsDNA targets and ssDNA collateral substrates traditionally recognized by Cas12a nucleases. Beginning with target recognition, we found that ReChb cleaved complementary dsDNA (**Fig. 3a**), ssDNA (**Fig. 3b**) and ssRNA (**Fig. 3c**) targets containing the reverse complement of the signature T-rich PAM sequence of canonical Cas12a substrates under *in vitro* conditions²⁴. While the dsDNA target encoded within a supercoiled plasmid was cleaved into a linearized form, the ssDNA and RNA targets were completely degraded. In contrast, FnCas12a completely cleaved the dsDNA and ssDNA targets and marginally cleaved the RNA target under the same conditions (**Extended Data Fig. 3**), in line with prior work¹⁴. We next turned to collateral substrate cleavage, now with the knowledge that ReChb could be activated by dsDNA, ssDNA or ssRNA. For all activating substrates, ReChb degraded non-target dsDNA (**Fig. 3d**), ssDNA (**Fig. 3e**), and ssRNA (**Fig. 3f**). FnCas12a degraded non-target ssDNA, but only in the presence of ssDNA and dsDNA targets (**Extended Data Fig. 3**). Interestingly, the closely related Cas12a2 (that shares 26% of sequence identity with ReChb) nucleases recognize RNA but not ssDNA targets and collaterally cleave ssRNA, ssDNA and dsDNA^{29,30}, suggesting that the ancestrally resurrected nuclease captures the targeting properties of both nucleases despite Cas12a and Cas12a2 respectively specializing in DNA and ssRNA target recognition and ASR only drawing from the Cas12a branch. Critically, the flexible targeting properties exhibited by ReChb extend beyond those of any individual characterized Cas nuclease found in modern organisms^{14,30-32}.

Based on the observed collateral cleavage activity of ReChb, we assessed ReChb as a tool for molecular diagnostics. Cas12a has been extensively used to for the detection of specific dsDNA and ssDNA sequences, with cleavage of ssDNA beacons for signal production³³. However, RNA remains a poor substrate for Cas12a, requiring workarounds such as supplying a partial dsDNA target²³. To explore the potential of ReChb, we incubated a ReChb-crRNA RNP complex with a dsDNA, ssDNA or ssRNA target as well as short ssRNA (**Fig. 3h**) and ssDNA (**Fig. 3i**) beacons fusing a fluorophore and quencher (**Fig. 3g**). All combinations of targets and molecular beacons resulted in increased fluorescence compared to no target. In contrast, an FnCas12a-crRNA RNP only yielded increased fluorescence when combining a dsDNA or ssDNA target with the ssDNA molecular beacon. Therefore,

ReChb could expand existing capabilities for CRISPR-based molecular diagnostics with a single nuclease capable of accepting different types of nucleic-acid biomarkers and molecular beacons.

Traditional CRISPR diagnostics systems based on collateral cleavage by Cas12 nucleases are restricted by the presence of PAM sequence before the target sequence, compromising the universal recognition of any target. Based on PAM-flexible recognition of ReChb, we envisioned that combining the collateral cleavage of ReChb next to its PAM-flexible recognition, we could overcome this main limitation of this technology. To test this hypothesis, we first compared the collateral cleavage of ReChb with those exposed by wild-type LbCas12a¹⁴, a widely used Cas12a nuclease for molecular diagnostics³³, after the recognition of a dsDNA target with a T-rich PAM (**Fig 4a**). The activity exhibited by ReChb (0.0045 AU/s) was lower to that of LbCas12a (0.0051 AU/s) under equivalent conditions (**Fig. 4b,d**) at 37°C. Reducing the temperature from 37°C to 25°C (room temperature, RT, **Supplementary Fig. 5**) significantly decreases the activity of both nucleases (**Fig. 4b**). However, at RT, ReChb retains its ability to recognize target substrates at low concentrations (2 pM, **Fig. 4c**) compared to LbCas12a which shows a higher detection limit (10 nM, **Fig. 4c**). This is in line with previously reported results, where higher temperatures yielded optimal cleavage activity for Cas12a nucleases^{34,35}. Thus, ReChb exhibits catalytic properties comparable to LbCas12a, a leading nuclease for CRISPR-based diagnostics while also offering PAM flexibility and measurable activity at room temperature well suited for point-of-care molecular diagnostics.

Given the ability of ReChb to recognize non-canonical PAMs with similar activities to that of LbCas12a, we applied ReChb in application requiring dsDNA recognition and PAM flexibility: detection of a short (21-bp) variable region of a single amplicon of 16S rDNA³⁶ (**Fig. 4e**). By applying this approach, it is possible to amplify the target region using universal primers that anneal to the conserved region of 16S rDNA and thus avoid difficulties associated with multiplexed pre-amplification. To evaluate this approach, we designed four different crRNAs that hybridizes to four variable regions (from hypervariable region V1) of bacterial 16S rDNA with a non-canonical PAM (GTCG). Importantly, this region does not possess a T-rich stretch and thus cannot be recognized by traditional Cas12a-based diagnostics. Specifically, we selected four bacterial pathogens, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, relevant pathogens associated with sepsis in newborns³⁶. Then, we evaluated the collateral cleavage activity for each 16S dsDNA fragment and each crRNA. We found that ReChb triggered fluorescence release only when there was a match between the dsDNA 16S fragment and the crRNA (**Fig. 4f**). As expected, LbCas12a was not able to recognize any of these DNA targets (**Supplementary Fig. 6**). We noticed crRNA from *K. pneumoniae* also triggered fluorescence release when paired with the other three pathogens, likely due to gRNA sequence similarity with seed region as previously reported³⁷. In fact, the mismatch profile analysis of ReChb showed that the protein did not tolerate single or double mismatches at positions 1-20, only triggering a reduced fluorescence signal to single mismatches at positions 7-20 nt or double mismatches at the end of the PAM distal region (**Supplementary Fig. 7**). However, this signal was significantly reduced compared to that displayed by ReChb with a target dsDNA substrate. These results demonstrate the specificity and flexibility of ReChb for molecular diagnostics.

Given ReChb's flexibility in target and collateral substrate recognition, we reasoned that ReChb could also exhibit flexibility in crRNA recognition. To determine the crRNA scaffold recognition determinants of ReChb, *in vitro* dsDNA cleavage assays were performed by incubating the enzyme with crRNAs from various CRISPR types and Cas12a species (**Extended Data Fig. 4a-c**). ReChb linearized plasmid DNA using targeting crRNAs from not only different Cas12a nucleases but also from Cas9 and Cas12j. The use of crRNAs with distinct repeats from different types and subtypes is not associated with modern CRISPR-Cas systems and at most was observed with the ancestral Cas9¹⁵. ReChb could also process its own precursor (pre-)crRNA comprising multiple crRNAs in the same transcript (**Extended Data Fig. 4d**). The pattern of cleavage products (65 nts) against a single customized pre-

crRNA transcript¹³ with four repeats matched with the expected length obtained from cutting the 5' end of a direct repeat hairpins²⁴. Thus, ReChb can process its own crRNA guides similar to type V effector nucleases^{38,39}, and it can share crRNAs with different types of Cas nucleases. This capability of ReChb should be relevant for multiplexed genome editing applications that employ customized CRISPR arrays for multi-site targeting¹³.

Structure of ReChb ternary complex

To shed light on the mechanism behind the flexibility of PAM and substrate recognition exerted by ReChb, we solved the cryo-EM structure of the nuclease effector bound to a crRNA and different substrates. The 3.1 Å resolution cryo-EM structure (PDB: 8QWE) captures a ternary complex of ReChb bound to crRNA and target dsDNA containing a T-rich PAM (**Fig. 5, Supplementary Figs. 8 and 9, Extended Data Table 1**). Overall ReChb displays a bilobed architecture resembling the characteristic oval “sea conch” shape described for Cas12a⁴⁰. The recognition (REC) lobe comprises both REC1 and REC2 domains, and the nuclease (NUC) lobe comprises the PAM-interacting (PI), wedge (WED), RuvC, Nuc and bridge helix (BH) domains (**Fig. 5a**). The crRNA-target DNA heteroduplex (R-loop, **Fig. 5b, Extended Data Fig. 5**) threads through the positively charged central channel between the two lobes. The target strand (TS) hybridizes with the crRNA, while the dissociated non-target strand (NTS) traces a straight path through the groove of the DNA nuclease site. There is unambiguous cryo-EM density downstream of the cleaved end of the TS, which we attribute to a post-cleavage product (**Figs. 5c,d**). As in Cas12a, the nuclease active site of ReChb lies in a pocket at the interface between Nuc and RuvC. The RuvC domain carries the three (D878, E967 and D1216) highly conserved active site residues (**Extended Data Fig. 6**). In contrast to other Cas12a nucleases^{31,41,42}, the nuclease site of ReChb embraces the dissociated NTS through stacking interactions with W1041 and F971 residues.

The tertiary structure also presented an opportunity to understand the basis of flexible PAM recognition. Both WED and PI domains grip the PAM region of the target dsDNA in a manner analogous to FnCas12a but with notable differences (**Fig. 5e,f**)⁴⁰. FnCas12a predominantly recognizes the PAM through multiple interactions between K671 and the minor-groove edge of the PAM duplex, employing a mechanism of base and shape readout from both the minor groove and major groove⁴¹. Notably, in the case of FnCas12a, only K671 interacts with the bases in the PAM region, indicating that shape may play a more pivotal role than direct base readout in PAM recognition^{40,41}. In contrast, ReChb achieves altered PAM recognition through newly formed electrostatic interactions between residues K124, K125, and K130 from the REC1 domain with the phosphate backbone of the PAM bases through the minor groove. A similar mechanism has already been described for engineered versions of AsCas12 (RVR and RR), which recognized TATV and TYCV, respectively^{20,43}. The structure of these engineered forms revealed that altered PAM recognition by these variants relies on newly formed interactions between substituted residues and the altered PAM-complementary nucleotides^{41,43}. Consequently, these findings could provide a structural framework for the flexible PAM readout exhibited by ReChb, reinforcing the notion that amino acid substitutions strengthening the PAM-binding channel could contribute to the alteration of Cas12a nucleases PAM specificity.

Continuing with the catalytic cycle of ReChb, Cas12a structural studies have suggested a reaction cycle coupled to conformational changes^{40,42,44,45}. The cycle begins with an apo state at equilibrium between closed and open conformations, where crRNA binding shifts the equilibrium to the closed form and target dsDNA causes a further structural tuning that includes the rearrangement of the bridge helix and helix 1 of the RuvC II sub-domain^{40,42,44,45}. These latter changes in RuvC are absent in the cryo-EM structure of the ReChb ternary complex, likely because the structure represents a post-cleavage form, and the nuclease might have reverted to a non-activated state. We note that the 3.3 Å resolution structure of apo ReChb (**Supplementary Note 1, Supplementary Figs. 10 and 11, Extended Table 1**) without a crRNA displays a ring-like architecture distinct from the closed oval “sea conch” shape of the ternary

complex (**Extended Data Fig. 7**) and from the open and closed conformations suggested for Cas12a in the apo state. The REC2 domain closes the ring by connecting with the RuvC domain in a way that hinders access to the nuclease active site (**Supplementary Fig. 11**), and the central channel between the recognition and nuclease lobes, where the crRNA-target DNA heteroduplex threads in the ternary complex, is not formed.

Structure of ReChb quaternary complex

The 3.0 Å resolution cryo-EM structure (PDB: 8QWF) (**Fig. 6, Supplementary Figs. 8 and 9, Extended Data Table 1**) of a quaternary complex of ReChb bound to crRNA, target dsDNA containing a T-rich PAM, and a non-specific collateral dsDNA with both strands contain non-hydrolysable phosphorothioate modifications (**Fig. 6a**), provides a framework to understand its collateral nuclease activity. As shown for Cas12a nucleases³¹, after cleavage, the target strand (TS) remains hybridized to the crRNA. However, the cryo-EM density for most of the dissociated non-target strand (NTS) is absent, indicating its displacement from the ternary complex pathway (**Fig. 6b and 6c**), maintaining the ReChb-crRNA complex in the catalytically activated conformation. Specifically, the structure captures RuvC in a pre-hydrolysis state, during which the non-hydrolysable collateral substrate, visible only at low density thresholds, is attempting to enter its active site (**Fig. 6d**). This weak density for the collateral substrate is consistent with a constant motion of the substrates, aligning with biochemical data showing dsDNA degradation occurring through multiple-turnover DNA nicking (**Fig. 3d**). Therefore, the conformational arrangements of the complex and the PAM-distal target DNA displacement increase accessibility to the RuvC active site, enabling rapid substrate capture and cleavage *in trans* as measured for ReChb (**Fig. 3**). In fact, with the notable exception of Cas12a2, other natural Cas12 nucleases have difficulties collaterally cleaving dsDNA substrates at short incubation times^{29,31,46}. This limitation has been attributed to the RuvC active site not being able to accommodate duplex DNA properly. In addition, the Nuc domain might also act as a physical barrier limiting cleavage *in trans*²⁹. Analogously to Cas12a2²⁹, ReChb can nick, linearize and degrade supercoiled non-specific plasmid DNA. Using FnCas12a as a reference, structures of FnCas12a post-cleavage state (PDB: 5MGA)⁴⁰ reveal that the presence of the crRNA-TS complex hinders the path to the catalytic site creating a narrow pathway to reach the RuvC active site, which is incompatible with rigid dsDNA substrates (**Extended Data Fig. 8**). This contrasts with the accessible ReChb RuvC active site in the post-cleavage state, offering a structural basis for the wide range of collateral substrates degraded by ReChb (**Extended Data Fig. 8**). In fact, this mechanism resembles that of Cas12a2, where the absence of Nuc domain and the presence of an exposed RuvC active site afford high substrate accessibility, enabling the cleavage a wide range of substrates *in trans*²⁹. Overall, the structural determination together with the biochemical assays highlight the versatility of ReChb for substrate recognition as well as nucleic-acid editing.

Discussion

Protein design techniques using computational methods offer an opportunity to improve and even design catalysts with properties not found in natural enzymes⁴⁷. The increasing number of protein sequences in databases and the advent of new methods for sequence alterations and design, including deep-learning methods and language models⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰, have the potential to expand the universe of biomolecules and revolutionize the fields of biotechnology and synthetic biology. ASR is rapidly gaining prominence in this context, as it not only provides important evolutionary information, but also is able to generate novel protein sequences not found today⁵¹⁻⁵⁵. ASR is arguably the only technique that can handle non-natural sequences with many residues (>1,000) and with substantial identity alterations relative to natural proteins.

We previously established that ASR can be utilized to uncover important aspects of the evolution of CRISPR-Cas systems¹⁵. What we present here goes a step further, demonstrating that it is possible

to obtain a nuclease with a set of properties that have not been found yet in any existing natural Cas nuclease, surpassing the functionality and versatility of any known Cas nuclease. As shown before¹⁵, ancestral proteins display a functional promiscuity that is clearly present in ReChb perhaps as its most prominent feature. ReChb can recognize any nucleic-acid form as a target and is able to carry out specific or non-specific *cis/trans* cleavage. This can be accomplished without the need for the recognition of a strict PAM and with a variety of crRNA-guide sequences. ReChb can process its own crRNA and is proficient at genome editing in human cells at a wide range of sites. Another aspect relevant to note is that the promiscuity of ReChb towards nucleic acids could lead to cell toxicity when it is applied as genome editing tool. In this case, as observed with other Cas12a nucleases⁵⁶, no signs of cell toxicity have been detected during cell experiments. This suggests that these promiscuous collateral activities are likely only observed *in vitro* and do not negatively impact the protein's on-target activity *in vivo*. Although ReChb is capable of collateral cleavage of ssRNA, our hypothesis is that, unlike Cas13, ReChb binds to its DNA target, which limits its ability to freely diffuse and affect surrounding RNA. The cryo-EM structures provide a framework to understand the differences between synthetic ReChb and natural Cas nucleases, and for further finetuning as a biotechnology tool. Importantly, all of these new features have been readily achieved using ASR, unlike other protein design techniques based on rational design where only one feature is improved at a time. This is clearly exemplified, for example, in the effort made to achieve relaxed recognition of PAM using protein engineering techniques such as that performed for enAsCas12a rather than the ease of ASR. On the other hand, in terms of evolution, the different promiscuous features found in the ancestors of Cas9¹⁵ and Cas12 reveal that the exact connections between them are unknown and hidden, and surely interconnected mechanisms are yet to be discovered.

In practical terms, the versatility of ReChb makes it unique and versatile, as it can be used for both genome editing and diagnostics based on nucleic-acid detection. In recent years, assays based on the collateral activity of Cas12a and Cas13 have been developed as diagnostic tools³³. Cas12a and Cas13 can only be efficiently activated by DNA and RNA, and thus depending on the sequence to be detected one enzyme or the other normally must be used. ReChb is not limited in this way, as it can be activated by any nucleic acid and is thus able to identify any type of genetic target. In addition, we demonstrate that the PAM-flexible recognition ability of ReChb allows overcoming one of the main limitations of Cas12-based diagnostic, i.e., recognition of dsDNA targets without the PAM restriction. To the best of our knowledge, ReChb is the only reported nuclease with such expanded activities (**Supplementary Table 1**). A nuclease with these features might well exist in nature, but searching the natural enzyme space could prove arduous, costly and time-consuming. Similarly, machine learning-based computational methods are still in their infancy and are not yet capable of designing enzymes with complex and controlled functions such as large-scale conformational changes. The recent developed deep-learning methods (OpenCRISPR-1⁵⁷), while promising, have not yet demonstrated the ability to design proteins with new functionalities. These limitations highlight the importance of ASR to generate complex synthetic enzymes with multiple and improved properties opening new avenues for its inclusion and combination with deep-learning and language methods.

Methods

Engineering of ReChb sequence

ReChb was engineered through computational methodologies, specifically, ancestral sequence resurrection (ASR)¹⁵. We use the BLAST tool with custom parameters and criteria—that is, a maximum of 1,000 hits and minimum identity 35% to ensure the selection of Cas12a sequences (individually inspected) and BLOSUM62 scoring matrix. E-values were virtually zero for all sequences. Sixty-three sequences were selected following similar proportions of sequences in each phylum as in the database

(Extended Figure 1). Sequences belong to five bacterial phyla: *Pseudomonadota*, *Planctomycetota*, *Spirochaetota*, *Bacteroidota* and *Bacillota*, as outgroup. Alignment of sequences was performed using MUSCLE software on the MEGA platform and manually edited to eliminate gaps, poorly aligned sites and divergent regions. We inferred the best evolutionary model using MEGA, resulting in the JTT with gamma distribution model (eight categories), Yule model for speciation and length chain of 100 million generations, sampling every 1,000 generations. Phylogeny was carried out using BEAST v.2.6.6 package software (<https://beast.community/>) including the BEAGLE library for parallel processing and based on Bayesian inference using MCMC. Divergence times were estimated using the Reltime method⁵⁸ implemented in MEGA with discrete eight-category Gamma distribution for evolutionary rates. We set calibration times using information from the TToL^{25,59} in three major clades with 95% confidence interval (CI). Finally, ancestral sequence reconstruction was performed by maximum likelihood using PAML v.4.9 (<http://abacus.gene.ucl.ac.uk/software/paml.html>) with a gamma distribution of eight categories for variable replacement rates across sites. Posterior probabilities were calculated for all amino acids, and the residue with highest posterior probability was chosen for each site. The reconstructed sequence displays average posterior probability of 0.92 and amino acid sequence identities of 52 % with respect to FnCas12a and 26% with respect to SuCas12a2.

***In vitro* characterization**

Expression and purification of ReChb. The ReChb gene was synthesized and codon-optimized for *E. coli* cell expression. ReChb was cloned in pET-28a(+) expression vector and transformed in *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) (Life Technologies) for protein expression. Cells were incubated in LB medium at 30 °C at 160 rpm until OD600 reached 0.6 and IPTG (400 µM) was added for protein induction overnight at 18 °C. Cells were pelleted by centrifugation at 5000 g. Pellets were resuspended in extraction buffer (Tris 50 mM, NaCl 500 mM, pH 8, Imidazole 10 mM) supplemented with EDTA Free protease inhibitor (Thermo). Then, the pellet was sonicated for 3 cycles for 10 min at 30% amplitude. Cell debris was separated by ultracentrifugation at 33,000 G for 1 h. For purification, the supernatants were mixed with Ni-NTA agarose beads (Thermo) and incubated for 1 hour. Then, the beads were washed with 50 x column volumes with 40 mM imidazole. After that, imidazole concentration was reduced to 10 mM and aliquot of protease 3C was added. After 1 hour of incubation, protein was eluted in elution buffer (Tris-HCl 50 mM, NaCl 500 mM, pH 8, Imidazole 10 mM). The protein was further purified by size exclusion chromatography using a Superose 6 10/300 GL column (GE Healthcare) and eluted in 50 mM Tris pH 7.5, 150 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂. For protein purification verification, sodium dodecyl sulphate–polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS–PAGE) was used with 8% gels. The protein concentration was calculated by measuring the absorbance at 280 nm in Nanodrop 2000C.

crRNA synthesis. crRNA (**Supplementary Table 2**) was synthesized using a HiScribe T7 High Yield RNA Synthesis Kit (NEB). The DNA sequences includes the T7 promoter at the 5' end and the sequence from crRNA with the target sequence at the 3' end. ssDNA oligos were hybridized and the reaction was incubated overnight. Then the crRNA was purified following the protocol of the Monarch RNA Purification Columns Kit.

Nucleic acid cleavage assays. For analysis of targeted cleavage (Supplementary Table 3) on supercoiled DNA, 30 µL reactions of 170 nM of ReChb-crRNA and 100 nM of dsDNA target in 1 x NEB 3.1 buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.9, 100 mM NaCl, 10 mM MgCl₂, 100 µg ml⁻¹ BSA) were incubated at 37 °C for varying incubation times. In the case of ssDNA substrate, 30 µL reactions of 80 nM of ReChb-crRNA and 30 nM of ssDNA target in 1 x NEB 3.1 buffer were incubated at 37 °C for varying incubation times. Reactions were stopped by adding 6X loading dye (NEB) with EDTA and running 1-2% agarose gel. Gels were dyed with SYBR gold (ThermoFisher) and imaged with ChemiDoc XRS + System (Bio-Rad). Cleavage was quantified by ImageJ. Finally, for ssRNA targeted cleavage, 30 µL reactions of 250 nM of ReChb-crRNA and 120 nM of ssRNA target in 1 x NEB 3.1 buffer were incubated at 37 °C for

different varying times. Reactions were stopped by adding 2X loading dye (NEB) with EDTA and running 10% TBE polyacrylamide gels. Gels were dyed with SYBR gold (ThermoFisher) and imaged with ChemiDoc XRS + System (Bio-Rad). Cleavage was quantified by ImageJ.

For analysis of non-targeted (collateral or *trans*) cleavage (Supplementary Table 4, 5), 30 μ L reactions of 70 nM of ReChb-crRNA, 70 nM of target substrate (dsDNA, ssDNA or ssRNA) and 120 nM of collateral substrate (dsDNA, ssDNA or ssRNA) in 1 x NEB 3.1 were incubated at 37 °C for varying incubation times. Reactions were stopped by adding 2X loading dye (NEB) with EDTA or 6X loading dye (NEB) with EDTA and running 10% TBE polyacrylamide gels or 1-2% agarose gel, respectively. Gels were dyed with SYBR gold (ThermoFisher) and imaged with ChemiDoc XRS + System (Bio-Rad). Cleavage was quantified by ImageJ.

PAM library construction. A DNA library (Supplementary Table 6, 7) comprising seven random nucleotides was created and subsequently cloned into the plasmid pUC18 by GenScript. This random library was transformed in XL1blue *E. coli* and amplified several times to achieve maximal variability in the PAM sequences. Subsequently, an 855 bp PCR fragment was generated using the primers detailed in Supplementary Table 7 from the DNA library containing the seven random nucleotides.

PAM determination. PAM determination assay was performed incubating of 170 nM of ReChb-crRNA (targeting 23 nt downstream the 7 random nucleotides) and 100 nM of PCR fragment from the DNA library in 1 x NEB 3.1 buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.9, 100 mM NaCl, 10 mM MgCl₂, 100 μ g ml⁻¹ BSA) for 1 hour at 37 °C. Reaction was stopped added 6X loading dye (NEB) with EDTA and run 2% agarose gel. Gels were dyed with SYBR gold (ThermoFisher) and imaged with ChemiDoc XRS + System (Bio-Rad). The longer fragment, that contained the 7 random nucleotides, was purified from the agarose gel with GeneJet Gel Extraction kit (ThermoFisher) and sequenced by Ion Torrent and the obtained reads were mapped in the reference sequence. Each PAM sequence was quantified, and its frequency calculated from the total PAM previously extracted. From the frequency of each PAM, PAM wheel was generating, following previously published methodology⁶⁰.

For *in vitro* cleavage of different PAM sequences, different DNA fragments carrying each PAM (Supplementary Table 8) were cloned into Zero-Blunt TOPO plasmid. The cleavage assay was performed under the conditions described previously. For FAM-labelled dsDNA substrates (Supplementary Table 3), the results were analysed using 15% urea-PAGE gel and visualized for fluorescein fluorescence.

pre-crRNA processing. pre-crRNA arrays (Supplementary Table 9 and 10) were synthesized using the HiScribe T7 High Yield RNA Synthesis Kit (NEB). T7 transcription was performed for 16 h and then RNA was purified using the Monarch RNA Cleanup Kit (NEB). *In vitro* cleavage was performed with purified recombinant. ReChb (330 nM) and *in vitro*-transcribed pre-crRNA arrays (100 nM) were incubated at 37 °C 1 x NEB 3.1 buffer for 1 hour. Reactions were stopped by adding 2X loading dye (NEB) with EDTA and running 10% TBE polyacrylamide gels. Gels were dyed with SYBR gold (ThermoFisher) and imaged with ChemiDoc XRS + System (Bio-Rad).

Nucleic acid detection by ReChb with ssRNA and ssDNA reporter probes.

For nucleic acid detection using fluorescent reporter probes, a 70 nM concentration of the ReChb-crRNA complex was combined with RNase or DNase Alert (250 nM, IDT) and a 70 nM concentration of the target substrate (dsDNA, ssDNA, or ssRNA) for 2 hours and 30 minutes at 37°C, respectively. The trans-cleavage assay was performed in 100 μ L reactions and the resulting end-point fluorescence was measured using a multi-mode microplate reader (BioTek Instruments), with excitation/emission wavelengths of 490/520 nm for RNase Alert and 500/560 nm for DNase Alert. A negative control was prepared using nuclease-free water instead of the nucleic acid target.

For ReChb comparison with LbCas12a, the wild-type LbCas12a was purified using pMBP-LbCas12a expression plasmid [pMBP-LbCas12a was a gift from Jennifer Doudna (Addgene plasmid # 113431; <http://n2t.net/addgene:113431>; RRID:Addgene_113431)]. Protein purification was conducted as previously described¹⁴ and the protein stocks were diluted into storage buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, 300 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT, 0.1 mM EDTA, 500 µg/ml BSA, 50% Glycerol, pH 7.5) at 1 µM. For in vitro collateral cleavage assay, purified proteins (ReChb and LbCas12a, 100 nM), gRNA (100 nM), target dsDNA (10, 2, 0.2, 0.02, 0.002 nM, respectively) and single-strand DNA reporter (DNase alert, 1000 nM, IDT) were added into 1 x NEB r2.1 (Supplementary Table 11). The trans-cleavage assay was performed in 5 µL reactions by measuring the fluorescence on a multi-mode microplate reader (BioTek Instruments), using a 96-well V bottom plate (Thermo) with excitation/emission wavelengths 500/560 nm. Time-courses were run for 2 h with an interval of 1 min between reads. Observed rates were obtained by regression analysis of the linear regions of the progress curves. A negative control was prepared using nuclease-free water instead of the nucleic acid target.

For 16S rDNA detection of multiple pathogens related with sepsis, purified proteins (ReChb and LbCas12a, 100 nM), gRNA (100 nM), target dsDNA fragments (10 nm) and single-strand DNA reporter (DNase alert, 1000 nM, IDT) were added into 1 x NEB r2.1 (Supplementary Table 11).

For one-single mismatch and two mismatch profile of ReChb, purified ReChb (100 nM), gRNA (100 nM), target dsDNA fragments with one or two mismatches across target site (10 nm, Supplementary Table 12) and single-strand DNA reporter (DNase alert, 1000 nM, IDT) were added into 1 x NEB r2.1.

In cell characterization

Endogenous gene editing in human cells. Cells were maintained in DMEM (Gibco) supplemented with 10% heat inactivated FBS (Gibco) in an incubator at 37 °C and 5% CO₂. For plasmid transfection experiments, HEK293T cells were seeded onto 24-well plates (Thermo) 24 h before transfection. Cells were transfected using jetPrime (Polyplus) at 70–80% confluency following the manufacturer's recommended protocol. For each well of a 24-well plate, a total of 500 ng plasmid DNA (humanized version of ReChb cloned into pcDNA3.1, Addgene plasmid 69976 for FnCas12a [pY004 (pcDNA3.1-hFnCpf1) was a gift from Feng Zhang (Addgene plasmid # 69976 ; <http://n2t.net/addgene:69976> ; RRID:Addgene_69976)] and Addgene plasmid 107941 for enAsCas12a [pCAG-enAsCas12a(E174R/S542R/K548R)-NLS(nuc)-3xHA (AAS848) was a gift from Keith Joung & Benjamin Kleinstiver (Addgene plasmid # 107941 ; <http://n2t.net/addgene:107941> ; RRID:Addgene_107941)]) and 300 ng of PCR amplicons comprised of a U6 promoter driving expression of the different crRNA scaffolds for targeted each gene target sites were used (Supplementary Table 13 and 14).

HEK293T cells were transfected with DNA, as described above. Cells were incubated at 37 °C for 48 h after transfection before genomic DNA extraction. Genomic DNA was extracted using the GENELUTE™ mammalian genomic DNA Miniprep kit (Merck) following the manufacturer's protocol. The genomic DNA was PCR amplified and, after validating amplification on a 1% agarose gel, the amplicon was prepared for Sanger sequencing with the primer closest to the expected cleavage site. The chromatograms obtained from each sequencing reaction were analyzed using TIDE analysis²⁷. As an alternative, editing activity of ReChb was also evaluated using EnGen Mutation Detection Kit (NEB). Briefly, the genomic region flanking the target site for each gene was PCR amplified (Supplementary Table 13) using Q5® Hot Start High Fidelity and PCR products were subjected to a re-annealing process to enable heteroduplex formation. After re-annealing, products were treated with T7 endonuclease I, and analyzed on 2 % agarose gels. Gels were dyed with SYBR gold (ThermoFisher) and imaged with ChemiDoc XRS + System (Bio-Rad). Cleavage was quantified by ImageJ. Quantification was based on relative band intensities. Indel percentage was determined by the formula,

$$\% \text{ Indels} = 100 \times \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{(b+c)}{(a+b+c)}}\right),$$

where a is the integrated intensity of the undigested PCR product band, and b and c are the integrated intensities of each cleavage product band.

For RNP experiments in HeLa and Hs27 fibroblast cells, RNPs were complexed by mixing 70 pmol of ReChb and 140 pmol gRNA (Supplementary Table 14) in 50 μ l Opti-MEM at room temperature for 15 min. Then, RNPs were mixed with 4 μ l CRISPRMAX and 2.5 μ l Cas9 Plus reagent (Invitrogen), and then carefully dropped into existing cell culture media for transfection. Cells were incubated at 37 °C for 48 h after transfection before genomic DNA extraction. Genomic DNA was extracted using the GENELUTE™ mammalian genomic DNA Miniprep kit (Merck) following the manufacturer's protocol. The genomic DNA was PCR amplified and, after validating amplification on a 1-2% agarose gel, the amplicon was prepared for Sanger sequencing with the primer closest to the expected cleavage site. The chromatograms obtained from each sequencing reaction were analyzed using TIDE analysis²⁷.

For off-target analysis, predicted off-target sites in the genome using Cas-OFFinder²⁸ were PCR amplified with the primers listed in Source of Data 2, and, after validating amplification on a 1-2% agarose gel, the amplicon was prepared for Sanger sequencing with the primer closest to the expected cleavage site. The chromatograms obtained from each sequencing reaction were analyzed using TIDE analysis²⁷.

Cryo-EM structural determination

Cryo-EM data collection. For all specimens (see Supplementary Note 2 for details on specimen preparation), immediately after adding 0.05% CHAPS, 4 μ l aliquot of the mixture was adsorbed onto a glow-discharged Quantifoil R 1.2/1.3 300 mesh grid (Quantifoil) and vitrified in liquid ethane with a Leica EM GP2 cryoplunger (Leica) using front-side blotting for 2 s at 95% humidity. The vitrified complex specimens were imaged in house using a 300 kV Krios G4 (ThermoScientific) equipped with a BioContinuum/K3 camera (Gatan) operating in counting mode at a calibrated 0.8238 Å/pix. Employing a 1-1.6 μ m underfocus range we recorded three movies per hole with a total accumulated dose of 50 e⁻/Å² over 50 frames. Movies were recorded automatically using EPU 2 (ThermoScientific) with Aberration-free image shift (AFIS) and Fringe-free imaging (FFI).

Cryo-EM data processing. Initial processing of complex specimen data followed the same general processing strategy (Supplementary Figs. 8 and 10). Initial frame alignment and contrast transfer function (CTF) estimation was performed using cryoSPARC live⁶¹. Following processing steps were carried out in cryoSPARC⁶¹. (See Supplementary Figs. 8-10 and Supplementary Note 2 for details on the cryo-EM data processing and 3D reconstruction).

Model building. Initial models were obtained using automated model building with ModelAngelo⁶², and completed by manual intervention in Coot⁶³ (See Supplementary Note 2 for details). To improve the fit and to optimize stereochemistry of the atomic model real space refinements with secondary structure and geometry restraints were performed using Phenix⁶⁴.

Statistics and reproducibility

Results are representative of least two independent experiments. All replication attempts showed similar results.

Data Availability

We have made available sequencing data. Other data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request. Sequencing data for PAM determination and gene editing experiments will be made available through the National Center for Biotechnology Information Sequence Read Archive (NCBI SRA) under BioSample accessions SAMN38227368, SAMN38227369. The EM maps of apo ReChb, accession numbers EMD-18691 and EMD-18692, and its ternary and quaternary complexes, EMD-18693 and EMD-18694 have been deposited in the Electron Microscopy Data Bank (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/emdb/>). The atomic coordinates of ReChb, and its ternary and quaternary complexes, have been deposited in the Protein Data Bank (www.pdb.org) under PDB ID codes 8QWD, 8QWE and 8QWF, respectively.

Acknowledgments

This work has been supported by grants PID2019-109087RB-I00 and PID2022-141347OB-I00 to R.P.-J, PID2019-104423GB-I00 and PID2022-143177NB-I00 to I. U.-B, PID2021-126263OA-I00 to G. A.-P. funded by Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 964764 to R.P.-J and from a European Research Council Consolidator Award (grant agreement No 865973) to C. L. B. The content presented in this document represents the views of the authors, and the European Commission has no liability in respect to the content. Y.J. acknowledges financial support from Juan de la Cierva program grant FJC2021-047689-I funded by Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033) and by European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR. R.P.-J. and Y.J. acknowledge financial support from Spanish Foundation for the promotion of research of Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (FUNDELA). JPL-A acknowledges financial support from a PTA contract granted by the MCIN/AEI. CIC bioGUNE support was provided from The Department of Industry, Tourism and Trade of the Government of the Autonomous Community of the Basque Country (Elkartek Research Programs 2020-2023), the Innovation Technology Department of the Bizkaia County and MINECO for the Severo Ochoa Excellence Accreditation (CEX2021-001136-S). CIBERehd is funded by the Instituto de Salud Carlos III. High-resolution cryo-EM data collection was performed at the Basque Resource for Electron Microscopy supported primarily by the Department of Education and the Innovation Fund of the Basque Government, the Fundación Biofísica Bizkaia, and the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation, through the Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia (PRTR) funded by the NextGenerationEU (PRTR-C17.I1) program.

Author contributions

R. P.-J. conceived the project. R. P.-J., Y. J., I. T., I. U.-B. and C. L. B. designed research and planned experiments. Y. J. and R. P.-J. performed the phylogenetic analysis and ancestral sequence reconstruction. Y. J. and S.S., cloned and expressed proteins and performed in vitro experiments, functional validation of α -synCas in mammalian and bacterial cells. Y. J., M.G-L and A.M.A. performed the sequencing experiments and bioinformatic analysis. I. T., J.P. L.-A., G. A.-P. and I. U.-B. designed, performed, analysed and represented structural data. All authors participated in discussions and provided ideas for the work. Y. J., I.T., C. L. B., I. U.-B. and R.P.-J. wrote the manuscript with additional input end editions from all authors.

Competing interests

R. P.-J., Y.J. are co-inventors on patent application filed by CIC bioGUNE. C. L. B. is a co-founder and member of the Scientific Advisory Board for Locus Biosciences as well as a member of the Scientific Advisory Board for Benson Hill. There are no competing interests for all other authors.

Jabalera, Y., Tascón, I., Samperio, S. et al. A resurrected ancestor of Cas12a expands target access and substrate recognition for nucleic acid editing and detection. *Nat Biotechnol* 43, 1663–1672 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-024-02461-3>

Additional information

Extended data is available for this paper through the National Center for Biotechnology Information Sequence Read Archive (NCBI SRA) under BioSample accessions SAMN38227368, SAMN38227369.

Supplementary information

The online version contains supplementary material available at...

Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to Iban Ubarretxena-Belandia ivan.ubarrechena@ehu.es or Raul Perez-Jimenez: raulpj@icbiogune.es

References

- 1 Hampton, H. G., Watson, B. N. J. & Fineran, P. C. The arms race between bacteria and their phage foes. *Nature* **577**, 327-336, doi:10.1038/s41586-019-1894-8 (2020).
- 2 Makarova, K. S. *et al.* Evolutionary classification of CRISPR-Cas systems: a burst of class 2 and derived variants. *Nat Rev Microbiol* **18**, 67-83, doi:10.1038/s41579-019-0299-x (2020).
- 3 Barrangou, R. *et al.* CRISPR provides acquired resistance against viruses in prokaryotes. *Science* **315**, 1709-1712, doi:10.1126/science.1138140 (2007).
- 4 Karginov, F. V. & Hannon, G. J. The CRISPR system: small RNA-guided defense in bacteria and archaea. *Mol Cell* **37**, 7-19, doi:10.1016/j.molcel.2009.12.033 (2010).
- 5 Wang, J. Y. & Doudna, J. A. CRISPR technology: A decade of genome editing is only the beginning. *Science* **379**, eadd8643, doi:10.1126/science.add8643 (2023).
- 6 Hsu, P. D., Lander, E. S. & Zhang, F. Development and applications of CRISPR-Cas9 for genome engineering. *Cell* **157**, 1262-1278, doi:10.1016/j.cell.2014.05.010 (2014).
- 7 Jinek, M. *et al.* A programmable dual-RNA-guided DNA endonuclease in adaptive bacterial immunity. *Science* **337**, 816-821, doi:10.1126/science.1225829 (2012).
- 8 Koonin, E. V., Makarova, K. S. & Zhang, F. Diversity, classification and evolution of CRISPR-Cas systems. *Curr Opin Microbiol* **37**, 67-78, doi:10.1016/j.mib.2017.05.008 (2017).
- 9 Koonin, E. V., Gootenberg, J. S. & Abudayyeh, O. O. Discovery of Diverse CRISPR-Cas Systems and Expansion of the Genome Engineering Toolbox. *Biochemistry*, doi:10.1021/acs.biochem.3c00159 (2023).
- 10 Makarova, K. S. *et al.* Evolution and classification of the CRISPR-Cas systems. *Nat Rev Microbiol* **9**, 467-477, doi:10.1038/nrmicro2577 (2011).
- 11 Wang, J. Y., Pausch, P. & Doudna, J. A. Structural biology of CRISPR-Cas immunity and genome editing enzymes. *Nat Rev Microbiol* **20**, 641-656, doi:10.1038/s41579-022-00739-4 (2022).
- 12 Kim, D. *et al.* Genome-wide analysis reveals specificities of Cpf1 endonucleases in human cells. *Nat Biotechnol* **34**, 863-868, doi:10.1038/nbt.3609 (2016).
- 13 Zetsche, B. *et al.* Multiplex gene editing by CRISPR-Cpf1 using a single crRNA array. *Nat Biotechnol* **35**, 31-34, doi:10.1038/nbt.3737 (2017).
- 14 Chen, J. S. *et al.* CRISPR-Cas12a target binding unleashes indiscriminate single-stranded DNase activity. *Science* **360**, 436-439, doi:10.1126/science.aar6245 (2018).
- 15 Alonso-Lerma, B. *et al.* Evolution of CRISPR-associated endonucleases as inferred from resurrected proteins. *Nat Microbiol* **8**, 77-90, doi:10.1038/s41564-022-01265-y (2023).
- 16 Huang, H. *et al.* Engineered Cas12a-Plus nuclease enables gene editing with enhanced activity and specificity. *BMC Biol* **20**, 91, doi:10.1186/s12915-022-01296-1 (2022).
- 17 Kleinstiver, B. P. *et al.* Engineered CRISPR-Cas12a variants with increased activities and improved targeting ranges for gene, epigenetic and base editing. *Nat Biotechnol* **37**, 276-282, doi:10.1038/s41587-018-0011-0 (2019).

Jabalera, Y., Tascón, I., Samperio, S. *et al.* A resurrected ancestor of Cas12a expands target access and substrate recognition for nucleic acid editing and detection. *Nat Biotechnol* **43**, 1663–1672 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-024-02461-3>

- 18 Zhang, L. *et al.* AsCas12a ultra nuclease facilitates the rapid generation of therapeutic cell medicines. *Nat Commun* **12**, 3908, doi:10.1038/s41467-021-24017-8 (2021).
- 19 Toth, E. *et al.* Mb- and FnCpf1 nucleases are active in mammalian cells: activities and PAM preferences of four wild-type Cpf1 nucleases and of their altered PAM specificity variants. *Nucleic Acids Res* **46**, 10272-10285, doi:10.1093/nar/gky815 (2018).
- 20 Gao, L. *et al.* Engineered Cpf1 variants with altered PAM specificities. *Nat Biotechnol* **35**, 789-792, doi:10.1038/nbt.3900 (2017).
- 21 Tran, M. H. *et al.* A more efficient CRISPR-Cas12a variant derived from Lachnospiraceae bacterium MA2020. *Mol Ther Nucleic Acids* **24**, 40-53, doi:10.1016/j.omtn.2021.02.012 (2021).
- 22 Ma, E. *et al.* Improved genome editing by an engineered CRISPR-Cas12a. *Nucleic Acids Res* **50**, 12689-12701, doi:10.1093/nar/gkac1192 (2022).
- 23 Rananaware, S. R. *et al.* Programmable RNA detection with CRISPR-Cas12a. *Nat Commun* **14**, 5409, doi:10.1038/s41467-023-41006-1 (2023).
- 24 Zetsche, B. *et al.* Cpf1 is a single RNA-guided endonuclease of a class 2 CRISPR-Cas system. *Cell* **163**, 759-771, doi:10.1016/j.cell.2015.09.038 (2015).
- 25 Hedges, S. B. & Kumar, S. *The Timetree of Life*. (Oxford Univ. Press, 2009).
- 26 Tu, M. *et al.* A 'new lease of life': FnCpf1 possesses DNA cleavage activity for genome editing in human cells. *Nucleic Acids Res* **45**, 11295-11304, doi:10.1093/nar/gkx783 (2017).
- 27 Brinkman, E. K., Chen, T., Amendola, M. & van Steensel, B. Easy quantitative assessment of genome editing by sequence trace decomposition. *Nucleic Acids Res* **42**, e168, doi:10.1093/nar/gku936 (2014).
- 28 Bae, S., Park, J. & Kim, J. S. Cas-OFFinder: a fast and versatile algorithm that searches for potential off-target sites of Cas9 RNA-guided endonucleases. *Bioinformatics* **30**, 1473-1475, doi:10.1093/bioinformatics/btu048 (2014).
- 29 Bravo, J. P. K. *et al.* RNA targeting unleashes indiscriminate nuclease activity of CRISPR-Cas12a2. *Nature* **613**, 582-587, doi:10.1038/s41586-022-05560-w (2023).
- 30 Dmytrenko, O. *et al.* Cas12a2 elicits abortive infection through RNA-triggered destruction of dsDNA. *Nature* **613**, 588-594, doi:10.1038/s41586-022-05559-3 (2023).
- 31 Swarts, D. C. & Jinek, M. Mechanistic Insights into the cis- and trans-Acting DNase Activities of Cas12a. *Mol Cell* **73**, 589-600 e584, doi:10.1016/j.molcel.2018.11.021 (2019).
- 32 Abudayyeh, O. O. *et al.* C2c2 is a single-component programmable RNA-guided RNA-targeting CRISPR effector. *Science* **353**, aaf5573, doi:10.1126/science.aaf5573 (2016).
- 33 Kaminski, M. M., Abudayyeh, O. O., Gootenberg, J. S., Zhang, F. & Collins, J. J. CRISPR-based diagnostics. *Nat Biomed Eng* **5**, 643-656, doi:10.1038/s41551-021-00760-7 (2021).
- 34 Huyke, D. A. *et al.* Enzyme Kinetics and Detector Sensitivity Determine Limits of Detection of Amplification-Free CRISPR-Cas12 and CRISPR-Cas13 Diagnostics. *Anal Chem* **94**, 9826-9834, doi:10.1021/acs.analchem.2c01670 (2022).
- 35 Nalefski, E. A. *et al.* Kinetic analysis of Cas12a and Cas13a RNA-Guided nucleases for development of improved CRISPR-Based diagnostics. *iScience* **24**, 102996, doi:10.1016/j.isci.2021.102996 (2021).
- 36 Srinivasan, R. *et al.* Use of 16S rRNA gene for identification of a broad range of clinically relevant bacterial pathogens. *PLoS One* **10**, e0117617, doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0117617 (2015).
- 37 Chunlei Jiao, N. L. P., Jiaqi Yu, Mohammad Ghaem Maghami, Daphne Collias, & Sandra L. Martinez, R. L., Chase L. Beisel. TracrRNA reprogramming enables direct, PAM-independent detection of RNA with diverse DNA-targeting Cas12 nucleases. *Unpublished*.
- 38 Fonfara, I., Richter, H., Bratovič, M., Le Rhun, A. & Charpentier, E. The CRISPR-associated DNA-cleaving enzyme Cpf1 also processes precursor CRISPR RNA. *Nature* **532**, 517-521, doi:10.1038/nature17945 (2016).

- 39 Swarts, D. C., van der Oost, J. & Jinek, M. Structural Basis for Guide RNA Processing and Seed-Dependent DNA Targeting by CRISPR-Cas12a. *Mol Cell* **66**, 221-233 e224, doi:10.1016/j.molcel.2017.03.016 (2017).
- 40 Stella, S., Alcon, P. & Montoya, G. Structure of the Cpf1 endonuclease R-loop complex after target DNA cleavage. *Nature* **546**, 559-563, doi:10.1038/nature22398 (2017).
- 41 Yamano, T. *et al.* Crystal Structure of Cpf1 in Complex with Guide RNA and Target DNA. *Cell* **165**, 949-962, doi:10.1016/j.cell.2016.04.003 (2016).
- 42 Stella, S. *et al.* Conformational Activation Promotes CRISPR-Cas12a Catalysis and Resetting of the Endonuclease Activity. *Cell* **175**, 1856-1871 e1821, doi:10.1016/j.cell.2018.10.045 (2018).
- 43 Nishimasu, H. *et al.* Structural Basis for the Altered PAM Recognition by Engineered CRISPR-Cpf1. *Mol Cell* **67**, 139-147 e132, doi:10.1016/j.molcel.2017.04.019 (2017).
- 44 Strohkendl, I., Moy, C., Nguyen, A.-H., Russell, R. & Taylor, D. W. Structural basis of Cas12a R-loop propagation on pathway to DNA cleavage. *bioRxiv*, 2023.2003.2013.532460, doi:10.1101/2023.03.13.532460 (2023).
- 45 Worle, E., Newman, A., D'Silva, J., Burgio, G. & Grohmann, D. Allosteric activation of CRISPR-Cas12a requires the concerted movement of the bridge helix and helix 1 of the RuvC II domain. *Nucleic Acids Res* **50**, 10153-10168, doi:10.1093/nar/gkac767 (2022).
- 46 Murugan, K., Seetharam, A. S., Severin, A. J. & Sashital, D. G. CRISPR-Cas12a has widespread off-target and dsDNA-nicking effects. *J Biol Chem* **295**, 5538-5553, doi:10.1074/jbc.RA120.012933 (2020).
- 47 Hanreich, S., Bonandi, E. & Drienovska, I. Design of Artificial Enzymes: Insights into Protein Scaffolds. *Chembiochem* **24**, e202200566, doi:10.1002/cbic.202200566 (2023).
- 48 Yeh, A. H. *et al.* De novo design of luciferases using deep learning. *Nature* **614**, 774-780, doi:10.1038/s41586-023-05696-3 (2023).
- 49 Lovelock, S. L. *et al.* The road to fully programmable protein catalysis. *Nature* **606**, 49-58, doi:10.1038/s41586-022-04456-z (2022).
- 50 Madani, A. *et al.* Large language models generate functional protein sequences across diverse families. *Nat Biotechnol* **41**, 1099-1106, doi:10.1038/s41587-022-01618-2 (2023).
- 51 Manteca, A. *et al.* Mechanochemical evolution of the giant muscle protein titin as inferred from resurrected proteins. *Nat Struct Mol Biol* **24**, 652-657, doi:10.1038/nsmb.3426 (2017).
- 52 Perez-Jimenez, R. *et al.* Single-molecule paleoenzymology probes the chemistry of resurrected enzymes. *Nat Struct Mol Biol* **18**, 592-596, doi:10.1038/nsmb.2020 (2011).
- 53 Zakas, P. M. *et al.* Enhancing the pharmaceutical properties of protein drugs by ancestral sequence reconstruction. *Nat Biotechnol* **35**, 35-37, doi:10.1038/nbt.3677 (2017).
- 54 Risso, V. A., Gavira, J. A., Mejia-Carmona, D. F., Gaucher, E. A. & Sanchez-Ruiz, J. M. Hyperstability and substrate promiscuity in laboratory resurrections of Precambrian beta-lactamases. *J Am Chem Soc* **135**, 2899-2902, doi:10.1021/ja311630a (2013).
- 55 Risso, V. A. *et al.* De novo active sites for resurrected Precambrian enzymes. *Nat Commun* **8**, 16113, doi:10.1038/ncomms16113 (2017).
- 56 Marino, N. D., Pinilla-Redondo, R. & Bondy-Denomy, J. CRISPR-Cas12a targeting of ssDNA plays no detectable role in immunity. *Nucleic Acids Res* **50**, 6414-6422, doi:10.1093/nar/gkac462 (2022).
- 57 Ruffolo, J. A. *et al.* Design of highly functional genome editors by modeling the universe of CRISPR-Cas sequences. doi:10.1101/2024.04.22.590591 (2024).
- 58 Tamura, K. *et al.* Estimating divergence times in large molecular phylogenies. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **109**, 19333-19338, doi:10.1073/pnas.1213199109 (2012).
- 59 Kumar, S., Stecher, G., Suleski, M. & Hedges, S. B. TimeTree: A Resource for Timelines, Timetrees, and Divergence Times. *Mol Biol Evol* **34**, 1812-1819, doi:10.1093/molbev/msx116 (2017).

Jabalera, Y., Tascón, I., Samperio, S. *et al.* A resurrected ancestor of Cas12a expands target access and substrate recognition for nucleic acid editing and detection. *Nat Biotechnol* **43**, 1663–1672 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-024-02461-3>

- 60 Leenay, R. T. *et al.* Identifying and Visualizing Functional PAM Diversity across CRISPR-Cas Systems. *Mol Cell* **62**, 137-147, doi:10.1016/j.molcel.2016.02.031 (2016).
- 61 Punjani, A., Rubinstein, J. L., Fleet, D. J. & Brubaker, M. A. cryoSPARC: algorithms for rapid unsupervised cryo-EM structure determination. *Nat. Meth.* **14**, 290-296, doi:10.1038/nmeth.4169 (2017).
- 62 Jamali, K. *et al.* Automated model building and protein identification in cryo-EM maps. *bioRxiv*, doi:10.1101/2023.05.16.541002 (2023).
- 63 Emsley, P. & Cowtan, K. Coot: model-building tools for molecular graphics. *Acta Crystallogr D Biol Crystallogr* **60**, 2126-2132, doi:10.1107/S0907444904019158 (2004).
- 64 Afonine, P. V. *et al.* Real-space refinement in PHENIX for cryo-EM and crystallography. *Acta Crystallogr D Struct Biol* **74**, 531-544, doi:10.1107/S2059798318006551 (2018).

Figures

Figure 1. Ancestral sequence resurrection of Cas12a yields ReChb. (a) Phylogenetic tree of sequences used for ASR of ReChb. (b) The domain architecture of ReChb. REC, recognition; PI, protospacer adjacent motif (PAM) interacting; WED, wedge; BH, bridge helix; Nuc, nuclease. Both the WED and RuvC domains are formed by three discontinuous segments of the protein sequence. (Top) Aligned sequences associated with ReChb and representative Cas12a nucleases from REC1. (Bottom) Aligned sequences associated with ReChb and representative Cas12a nucleases from RuvC-II domain. Highlighted sequences indicated conserved positions mutated in ReChb.

Jabalera et al.

tests). NS difference for those target sites with PAMs recognized by enAsCas12 (i.e., 5'-TTTC-3', 5'-TTTG-3', 5'-TCCT-3', 5'-TCCC-3', 5'-TTAC-3') indicated as empty symbols.

Jabalera, Y., Tascón, I., Samperio, S. et al. A resurrected ancestor of Cas12a expands target access and substrate recognition for nucleic acid editing and detection. *Nat Biotechnol* 43, 1663–1672 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-024-02461-3>

Figure 3. Characterization ReChb activity *in vitro*. (a) *In vitro* DSB activity of ReChb against a 4,007 bp supercoiled plasmid DNA as a function of time. Exponential fit of the data expressed as % of cleaved product. (b) *In vitro* activity of ReChb against M13 phage derived ssDNA (M13 phage) as a function of time. Exponential fit of the data expressed as % of cleaved product. (c) *In vitro* activity of α -synCas against ssRNA as a function of time. Exponential fit of the data expressed as % of cleaved product. ReChb exhibits collateral activity against non-target nucleic acids *in vitro*. Time-course of collateral activity against non-target (d) dsDNA, (e) ssDNA, (f) ssRNA by an ReChb/crRNA complex activated with target dsDNA, ssDNA, and ssRNA substrates. Please refer to Extended Data Fig. 3 for the same characterization using FnCas12a as nuclease. (g) Nucleic acid detection assays. Quantification of maximum fluorescence signal generated after incubating ReChb-crRNA-activator with a custom (h) ssRNA-beacon or (i) ssDNA beacon for 2 hours and 30 min at 37°C, respectively. For FnCas12a sample, nuclease was target activated with a dsDNA substrate. The negative control was prepared using nuclease-free water instead of the nucleic acid target activator. Error bars represent the mean \pm SD, where n = 3. NS, P > 0.05; ***P < 0.001 (two-tailed Welch's t-tests).

Figure 4. ReChb as molecular diagnostic tool for PAM-free dsDNA target recognition. (a) Schematic of in vitro collateral cleavage assay for dsDNA recognition by ReChb. The ReChb-gRNA complex recognizes and cleavage the dsDNA target, which triggers non-specific collateral cleavage on ssDNA. (b) Sensitivity of ReChb and LbCas12a using a dsDNA with canonical PAM (5'-TTTC-3') as target substrate and ssDNA beacon as collateral substrate. Velocities were obtained by linear regression analysis of the linear regions of the progress curves. (c) Velocities for dsDNA target recognition and posterior collateral cleavage of ssDNA beacon by ReChb and LbCas12a at RT. (d) Velocities for dsDNA target recognition and posterior collateral cleavage of ssDNA beacon by ReChb and LbCas12a at 37°C. Error bars represent the mean \pm SD, where $n = 3$. NS: not significant, $P > 0.05$; *** $P < 0.001$ (two-tailed Welch's t-tests). (e) 16S dsDNA from four different pathogens including both conserved and variable region used for dsDNA target detection with non-canonical PAM sequence (5'-GTCG-3'). (f) Specific detection of pathogens based on 16S rDNA with ReChb and each specific crRNA using universal primers for specific amplification of variable region (yellow, V1) using conserved regions of 16S rDNA (blue). Ab: *Acinetobacter baumannii*; Ec: *Escherichia coli*; Kp: *Klebsiella pneumoniae*; Sa: *Staphylococcus aureus*. Error bars represent the mean \pm SD, where $n = 3$.

Figure 5. Ternary complex between ReChb, crRNA and target dsDNA. (a) Domain organization of ReChb. (b) Sequences of the crRNA guide and target strand and non-target strand DNA used to form the ternary complex. Nucleotides with coloured background are visible in the cryo-EM map, while uncoloured nucleotides are disordered. (c) Unsharpened cryo-EM map of the ternary complex coloured by nucleic acid and protein domain. Unassigned density attributed to the cleaved target strand is highlighted. (d) Cryo-EM structure of the ReChb ternary complex coloured and oriented as in c. A circle marks the putative location of the cleaved target strand. (e) Close-up view of the PAM region of the dsDNA highlighting the interactions with selected residues, shown as sticks, of the PI, WED, and REC1 domains. (f) Schematic of the interactions of target and non-target DNA strands of the PAM with FnCas12a (left) and ReChb (right).

Extended Figures

Extended Data Figure 1. Phylogenetic tree of sequences used for ASR of ReChb. Posterior probabilities for each node are indicated. A blue circle marks the node selected for ancestral sequence reconstruction.

Extended Data Figure 2. Editing activity of ReChb in human cells. (a) Editing activity in HEK293T cells. T7 endonuclease mismatch assay for genes *DNMT1*, *AAVS1* and *EMX1* mediated by ReChb and FnCas12a. (b) Quantification of indel efficiency achieved by ReChb at the target sites. Error bars represent the mean \pm SD, where n = 3.

Extended Data Figure 3. Activities of FnCas12a ortholog. Cleavage activity of FnCas12a against target (a) dsDNA, (b) ssDNA and (c) ssRNA. Collateral cleavage activity against non-target (d) dsDNA, (e) ssDNA and (f) ssRNA by an FnCas12a/crRNA complex activated by target nucleic-acid substrates.

Extended Data Figure 4. Flexible use of distinct crRNAs by ReChb while retaining pre-crRNA processing. (a) Target-dependent *in vitro* activity of ReChb using target crRNA (T), non-target crRNA (NT) and no-crRNA. *In vitro* cleavage assay against supercoiled dsDNA as a function of crRNAs from different CRISPR (b) types and (c) species. (d) *In vitro* processing of FnCas12a pre-crRNA (four repeats, 335 nt) transcript with purified FnCas12a and ReChb.

Extended Figure 5. Structures of the crRNA and target dsDNA in the ternary complex.

Extended Figure 6. Close-up of the ternary complex active site. On the left, the active site and lid-loop residues are shown as sticks and the non-target DNA strand nucleotides as filled sticks. A circle marks the putative location of the cleaved target strand DNA. On the right, the fitting of the active site region on the cryo-EM density map.

Extended Figure 7. Cryo-EM structure of apo ReChb. Comparison of apo (top) and ternary complex (bottom) structures of ReChb coloured by nucleic acid and protein domain. Arrows depict the direction of movement of the REC1 and REC2 domains upon RNA/DNA binding.

Extended Figure 8. Post-cleavage conformation of ReChb (left) and FnCas12a (right; PDB: 5MGA). Nucleotides are coloured as in **Figure 5b**.

Extended Table 1. Cryo-EM data collection, refinement and validation statistics.

	Apo ReChb (EMD-18691) (PDB 8QWD)	Ternary complex ReChb -crRNA- target dsDNA (EMD-18693) (PDB 8QWE)	Quaternary complex ReChb -crRNA- target dsDNA- collateral dsDNA (EMD-18694) (PDB 8QWF)
Data collection and processing			
Magnification	105000	105000	105000
Voltage (kV)	300	300	300
Electron exposure (e-/Å ²)	50.979	50.979	50.084
Defocus range (µm)	1-1.6	1-1.6	1-1.6
Pixel size (Å)	0.8238	0.8238	0.8238
Symmetry imposed	C1	C1	C1
Initial particle images (no.)	3324256	5463714	7589433
Final particle images (no.)	254316	137913	300509
Map resolution (Å)	3.33	3.14	3.08
FSC threshold	0.143	0.143	0.143
Map resolution range (Å)	2.9-6.5	2.9-6.5	2.9-6.5
Refinement			
Initial model used (PDB code)	-	-	-
Model resolution (Å)	3.3	3.1	3.0
FSC threshold	0.143	0.143	0.143
Model resolution range (Å)	2.9-6.5	2.9-6.5	2.9-6.5
Map sharpening <i>B</i> factor (Å ²)	-137.6	-103.2	-124.0
Model composition			
Non-hydrogen atoms	9204	11713	11499
Protein residues	1103	1185	1186
Ligands	2	5	6
<i>B</i> factors (Å ²)			
Protein	127.16	101.79	31.38
Nucleotide	-	93.27	35.04
Ligand	69.59	28.99	21.31
R.m.s. deviations			
Bond lengths (Å)	0.002	0.005	0.002
Bond angles (°)	0.507	0.645	0.499
Validation			
MolProbity score	1.79	1.63	1.69
Clashscore	8.29	6.94	7.59
Poor rotamers (%)	0.20	0.00	0.00
Ramachandran plot			
Favored (%)	95.02	96.33	95.99
Allowed (%)	4.98	3.67	4.01
Disallowed (%)	0.00	0.00	0.00